

Virtual Heat Plants as Flexibility Providers: Coordinating Hybrid Heating Systems via Monte Carlo Tree Search

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Abstract—Natural gas supplies over 80% of the UK’s residential heat demand through 23 million boilers, making domestic heating one of the largest obstacles to achieving net zero. Replacing these boilers with heat pumps would overload local electricity networks, particularly on cold days when everyone needs heat simultaneously. Hybrid systems help solve this problem. Pairing a heat pump with a backup gas boiler lets each household switch fuels depending on weather, price, and/or grid stress. The main benefits are not for individual households from this flexibility, but when multiple hybrids are coordinated as a single controllable resource, the aggregate effect can significantly alter network loading patterns. This paper presents a Virtual Heat Plant (VHP) framework that coordinates 20 hybrid households within a 100-dwelling neighbourhood in Edinburgh, Scotland, UK. We model both networks—electricity in *pandapower* and gas in *pandapipes*—using distribution parameters from Scottish Power and Scottish Gas Networks (SGN). Every half hour, a Monte Carlo Tree Search algorithm decides which homes should run on electricity and which should fire their boilers.

In the case study, the unmanaged operation of all heat pumps when temperatures drop sharply in cold January, demand forces the distribution feeder to 104.5% of its thermal limit. The VHP controller mitigates this violation by selectively shifting hybrid households to gas during critical periods, reducing peak loading to 86.3%, while still achieving 15.7% lower carbon emissions than gas-only operation. The optimised schedule adapts continuously: all hybrids run electrically during overnight periods of low demand, then progressively switch to gas as evening peaks approach. As a result, this work shows that coordinating just 20% of the neighbourhood allows enough headroom for the rest to electrify, hence decarbonising their heating demand.

Index Terms—Virtual Heat Plants, hybrid heating, Monte Carlo Tree Search, demand-side flexibility, heat decarbonisation, multi-energy networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Buildings consume around 40% of UK final energy; space heating and hot water alone account for roughly half of

household consumption [1]. Over 80% of this heat comes from natural gas, delivered through some 23 million domestic boilers. Achieving net-zero by 2050 in the UK and Scotland, which has set a higher goal of 2045, means replacing most of these installations with low-carbon alternatives. Heat pumps are the leading candidate, but mass electrification would burden distribution networks that were never designed for such loads. Upgrading grid infrastructure would require decades of work and billions of financial investment [2].

Hybrid heating systems provide a potential solution. Each unit combines a gas boiler and an air-source heat pump, enabling the household to use either gas when temperatures drop or network stress increases, or electricity when grid capacity and carbon intensity favours it [3]. Simulation studies confirm that during the coldest periods, the gas boiler can cover peak heating loads, allowing the heat pump to operate at lower supply water temperatures and consequently higher efficiency throughout the majority of the heating season [3].

Economically, the relevant comparison is not hybrid versus heat pump but hybrid versus a replacement gas boiler, the true counterfactual, since around 1.7 million gas boilers are installed in the UK annually [4]. Against this baseline, the additional cost of adding heat pump capability delivers a 65–70% reduction in carbon emissions and lower long-term running costs, without requiring fabric upgrades or grid reinforcement [4]. This flexibility exists at the device level, but its value emerges only through coordination. One household switching fuels has a negligible effect on a distribution feeder. Twenty switching together can reshape aggregate demand enough to relieve constraints and defer reinforcement.

Our earlier work introduced the Virtual Heat Plant (VHP) concept to capture this coordinated flexibility [5]. A VHP aggregates hybrid systems across multiple dwellings and dis-

patches them as a single controllable resource, adapting the Virtual Power Plant model [6] from distributed generation to multi-vector heating. Because hybrids draw from both gas and electricity, the coordination problem couples two networks: the controller must decide, at each time step, which households use which fuel while respecting network limits and balancing cost, carbon, and comfort.

We solve the coordination problem using Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS). MCTS builds a decision tree through repeated simulation, balancing exploration of new strategies against exploitation of known good ones [7]. Unlike model predictive control [8], it does not require a differentiable objective; unlike deep reinforcement learning [9], it needs no offline training [7]. Recent studies have applied MCTS to single-building heating control [10], [11], but these addressed one dwelling and one energy vector. Here, we scale tree search to 20 coupled households spanning two distribution networks.

The paper makes three contributions:

- 1) A modelling framework coupling 5R1C building thermal models with electric and gas network models, parameterised using Scottish Power and Scottish Gas distribution data.
- 2) An MCTS coordination algorithm whose reward function weights network security at 60%, ensuring the controller never accepts constraint violations in exchange for cost or carbon savings.
- 3) Empirical validation on an Edinburgh neighbourhood where 20 coordinated hybrids eliminate thermal limit violations under January 2025 extreme cold, reducing peak loading from 104.5% to 86.3% and cutting carbon by 15.7% versus gas-only operation.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodology combines three modelling layers with an optimisation module. Fig. 1 illustrates that building thermal models generate heat demand at dwelling resolution. Electric and gas network models, parameterised from Scottish Power and Scottish Gas distribution data, capture infrastructure constraints. The MCTS optimiser coordinates hybrid switching across a 24-hour horizon at 30-minute resolution (48 time steps).

A. Case Study Configuration

The case study is a 100-household residential neighbourhood in Edinburgh, Scotland, served by low-voltage electrical and low-pressure gas distribution networks. The neighbourhood captures a realistic decarbonisation snapshot, with 50 households heated by gas boilers, 30 by air-source heat pumps, and 20 by hybrid systems. The 20 hybrid households compose the Virtual Heat Plant, the controllable resource managed by the algorithm. The remaining 80 residences function in fixed modes, providing a background load.

The characteristics of the Scottish housing stock are derived from TABULA archetypes [12], which include detached, semi-detached, and terraced buildings. For occupancy, we apply the Load Profile Generator (LPG) [13], a stochastic tool

that generates realistic residential activity patterns based on demographic and behavioural data. Data from the Scottish Household Survey [14] and the Scotland Census 2022 [15] were used to build 100 household profiles for the Edinburgh case study.

B. Building and Thermal Models

The building model used in this work is the HiSim household infrastructure and building simulator [16] which is based on ISO 13790 quasi-steady-state method [17], using building data from TABULA project [12], a resistor-capacitor (RC) model [18]. The RC (5R1C) uses an analogy from an electrical circuit to explain thermal physics. Each household applies a single-zone 5R1C model, in which the building's thermal mass is represented by only one capacitance, while resistances are allocated to the walls, roof, floor, windows, and ventilation systems. The equation for heat balance is:

$$C_m \frac{dT_m}{dt} = \Phi_{\text{sol}} + \Phi_{\text{int}} + \Phi_{\text{HC}} - H_{\text{tr}}(T_m - T_e) \quad (1)$$

where C_m is effective thermal capacitance, T_m internal temperature, T_e external temperature, Φ_{sol} solar gains, Φ_{int} internal gains from occupants and appliances, Φ_{HC} heating system output, and H_{tr} the aggregate heat transfer coefficient. The equation is solved at half-hourly intervals with thermostat setpoints driven by occupancy: 20–21°C during occupied periods, 16–18°C during absences.

$$C_m \frac{dT_m}{dt} = \Phi_{\text{sol}} + \Phi_{\text{int}} + \Phi_{\text{HC}} - H_{\text{tr}}(T_m - T_e) \quad (2)$$

where C_m is effective thermal capacitance, T_m internal temperature, T_e external temperature, Φ_{sol} solar gains, Φ_{int} internal gains from occupants and appliances, Φ_{HC} heating system output, and H_{tr} the aggregate heat transfer coefficient. The equation is solved at half-hourly intervals with thermostat setpoints driven by occupancy: 20–21°C during occupied periods, 16–18°C during absences.

C. Heating Technology Models

Three heating technologies appear in the case study. Gas boilers convert natural gas to heat at 92% efficiency: $P_{\text{gas}}(t) = Q_{\text{heat}}(t)/\eta_b$, $\eta_b=0.92$. Heat pump electrical demand follows $P_{\text{el}}(t) = Q_{\text{heat}}(t)/\text{COP}(T_e)$, where $\text{COP}(T_e)$ is a quadratic fit to manufacturer data; lower temperatures reduce the COP. Hybrid systems can only operate in one mode at a time. The binary variable $h_i(t) \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates whether hybrid household i runs on gas ($h_i=1$) or electricity ($h_i=0$) at time t , giving:

$$P_i(t) = h_i P_{\text{gas},i}(t) + (1 - h_i) P_{\text{el},i}(t) \quad (3)$$

D. Network Models

The electric distribution network is modelled using pandapower [19], with topology and parameters derived from Scottish Power network data. The gas distribution network is modelled using pandapipes [20], parameterised from Scottish Gas data. The schematic representation of the coupled gas-electricity network case study, with dwellings mapped to

Fig. 1: Modelling framework for VHP coordination. Climate, occupancy, and building data feed the thermal model. Heating technology models convert thermal demand to gas and electric consumption. Network models evaluate distribution constraints. The MCTS optimiser determines hybrid switching decisions \mathbf{h}_t .

unique junctions and buses, as illustrated in Fig. 2. Both models are investigated to determine voltages, line loadings, pressures, and flow velocities for any specified demand configuration. To enable rapid evaluation during tree search, network states are pre-computed for two boundary configurations: all 20 hybrids on gas and all on electricity. Intermediate configurations are estimated by linear interpolation:

$$\hat{X}(t, k_t) = \frac{k_t}{20} X^{\text{gas}}(t) + \frac{20 - k_t}{20} X^{\text{el}}(t) \quad (4)$$

where $k_t = \sum_i h_i(t)$ counts hybrids operating on gas and X represents line loading, bus voltage, junction pressure, or pipe velocity. This interpolation captures the dominant effect: shifting hybrids between fuels changes gas and electric loading in opposite directions. The final selected schedule is verified against full network solutions.

E. MCTS Formulation

1) *State and Action Spaces*: The system state at time t comprises the hybrid configuration \mathbf{h}_t , aggregate gas and electric demands, network conditions, energy prices, and grid carbon intensity. Actions correspond to toggling individual houses: action $a \in \{0, 1, \dots, 19\}$ switches house a between gas and electric mode. This granular action space allows fine adjustment rather than coarse aggregate targets.

2) *Reward Function*: The reward function combines four objectives with priority-based weights:

$$r_t = 0.30 r_{\text{gas}} + 0.30 r_{\text{el}} + 0.25 r_{\text{cost}} + 0.15 r_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (5)$$

Network security receives 60% of the total weight because distribution infrastructure cannot tolerate overloads regardless of economic benefit. For the gas network, higher pressure

(a) Gas Network

(b) Electricity Network

Fig. 2: Schematic of the coupled gas-electricity network, with dwellings mapped to unique junctions and buses.

indicates greater supply margin; for the electric network, lower loading is preferable:

$$r_{\text{gas}} = \begin{cases} -100(0.9 - \rho_g)^2 & \text{if } \rho_g < 0.9 \\ 100(\rho_g - 0.9) & \text{if } \rho_g \geq 0.9 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$r_{\text{el}} = \begin{cases} -100(\rho_e - 0.8)^2 & \text{if } \rho_e > 0.8 \\ 100(0.8 - \rho_e) & \text{if } \rho_e \leq 0.8 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3: MCTS four phases per iteration: selection (UCB_1), expansion (new child), simulation (ϵ -greedy rollout, $d=8$, $\gamma=0.95$), and backpropagation. After $B=1000$ iterations, the most-visited child determines the action.

where $\rho_g = p/p_{\max}$ is normalised gas pressure and $\rho_e = L/L_{\max}$ is normalised line loading. The quadratic penalties create steep gradients near constraint boundaries.

Cost and carbon rewards use min-max normalisation:

$$r_{\text{cost}} = 10 \left(1 - \frac{C_t - C_{\min}}{C_{\max} - C_{\min}} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$r_{\text{CO}_2} = 10 \left(1 - \frac{E_t - E_{\min}}{E_{\max} - E_{\min}} \right) \quad (9)$$

where bounds are computed from the boundary configurations. All four components are clipped to $[-10, 10]$ before aggregation.

3) *Tree Search Procedure*: Fig. 3 illustrates the four MCTS phases. The algorithm iterates $B=1000$ times every time step. *Selection* descends from the root using Upper Confidence Bound for Trees:

$$UCB_i = \bar{r}_i + 1.8 \sqrt{\frac{\ln N}{n_i}} \quad (10)$$

where \bar{r}_i is the mean reward of child i , n_i its visit count, and N the parent visit count. The $c=1.8$ exploration constant was ascertained by initial testing.

Expansion adds one child node for an untried action. *Simulation* estimates future returns via ϵ -greedy rollout: with probability $\epsilon=0.2$ a random house is toggled; otherwise, all 20 toggles are evaluated and the best selected. Rollouts run for depth $d=8$ with a discount factor $\gamma=0.95$. *Backpropagation* updates visit counts and mean rewards along the path to the root.

After completing all iterations, the child with the highest visit count determines the action for that time interval. Then, the algorithm goes to the next time step.

III. RESULTS

The framework was tested in extreme cold weather on the day of January 31 in Edinburgh. Outdoor temperatures ranged from -2.5°C to $+0.5^\circ\text{C}$ (mean -1.1°C) [21], driving

Algorithm 1: MCTS-based VHP Coordination

Input: Initial configuration \mathbf{h}_0 , horizon $T=48$, iterations $B=1000$

Output: Schedule $\{\mathbf{h}_t^*\}_{t=1}^T$

```

1 for  $t = 1$  to  $T$  do
2   root  $\leftarrow$  Node(state  $s_t$ );
3   for  $b = 1$  to  $B$  do
4     node  $\leftarrow$  root;
5     while node fully expanded do
6       | node  $\leftarrow$  child maximising UCB;
7     end
8     if untried actions exist then
9       | node  $\leftarrow$  expand(node);
10    end
11     $R \leftarrow$  rollout(node.state);
12    backpropagate( $R$ );
13  end
14   $\mathbf{h}_t^* \leftarrow$  config of most-visited child;
15 end
16 return  $\{\mathbf{h}_t^*\}_{t=1}^T$ 

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sustained heating demand throughout the day. Grid carbon intensity varied between 25 and 175 gCO_2/kWh [22]; electricity prices from Octopus Agile tariff data for South Scotland ranged from 7.5 to 58.5 p/kWh [23], and gas prices followed Ofgem's Q1 2024 price cap rate of 8.04 p/kWh [24]. Three operating strategies are compared: all hybrids on gas, all hybrids on electricity, and MCTS-optimised switching.

A. Network Performance

Table I summarises network and environmental outcomes for the three strategies. Running all hybrids on electricity causes peak line loading to reach 104.5%, exceeding thermal capacity and triggering a constraint violation. Gas-only operation avoids this problem (73.1% peak loading), but it also gives up the carbon benefits of using a heat pump. The MCTS controller reduces peak loading to 86.3%, an 18 percentage

TABLE I: Performance Comparison Under Extreme Cold Conditions

Metric	Gas-only	Elec-only	MCTS
Peak line loading (%)	73.1	104.5	86.3
Thermal violations	0	1	0
Min bus voltage (pu)	0.972	0.951	0.960
Daily cost (£)	322.74	331.54	321.61
Daily CO ₂ (kg)	501.2	362.2	422.5
CO ₂ reduction vs. gas	—	27.7%	15.7%

point improvement over all-electric operation, eliminating the thermal violation. Gas network pressure remains within acceptable bounds (0.9996–0.9998 bar), and bus voltages stay above 0.95 pu throughout the day.

B. Cost and Carbon Performance

Daily operating cost under MCTS (£321.61) is marginally lower than gas-only (£322.74) and 3% below all-electric (£331.54). Cost savings are minimal; the principal advantage of coordination prioritises network security over economic gain.

Carbon emissions under MCTS total 422.5 kg CO₂, a 15.7% reduction compared to gas-only operation (501.2 kg). This falls short of the 27.7% reduction achievable with all-electric operation (362.2 kg). The gap reflects a fundamental constraint: maximising heat pump usage minimises carbon but causes network violations on cold days like this one. The controller accepts higher emissions to maintain infrastructure security.

C. Temporal Adaptation

Fig. 4 shows the time-varying behaviour of the optimised solution across three panels. Fig. 4a plots line loading (green) against the number of houses operating on gas (orange), with the 100% thermal limit shown as a dashed red line. Fig. 4b tracks half-hourly operating cost and carbon emissions throughout the day.

Not all 20 hybrid households run on gas at the same time; the controller decides how many should at any given hour based on how loaded the network is. In the early morning (04:00–07:00 am), only 4 to 6 households switch to gas, with the rest remaining on electricity since overnight demand poses little strain on the network. This number rises through the morning as electrical demand grows and reaches its highest point in the evening (17:00–22:00), where between 12 and 16 households are on gas at once. Around 18:00–19:00, demand temporarily eases, and the controller pulls back gas usage accordingly, though only briefly, as the evening peak quickly reasserts itself.

(a) Network loading and VHP configuration; the controller increases gas usage when loading rises, keeping it below the thermal limit.

(b) Cost and carbon emissions vary with electricity prices and grid carbon intensity.

Fig. 4: Time-varying optimisation behaviour of the MCTS controller.

Fig. 5: Individual house heating mode allocation: gas (red) and electric (green) across all 20 hybrid houses over 24 hours.

D. Switching Behaviour

Individual house switching patterns are shown in Fig. 5 as a heatmap, in which green denotes electric mode and red gas mode. Gas is mostly used in houses H1 through H6 for extended periods, whereas houses H15 to H20 mainly use electricity. This pattern occurs as the optimiser determines which houses significantly influence network loading based on their geographical location within the distribution network.

Fig. 6a shows the distribution of gas house counts across all time periods. The distribution is right-skewed with a peak around 10–14 houses, reflecting that the controller typically operates with more than half the hybrids on gas during this cold day. The mean of 8.8 lies below the mode because of the overnight periods when all or most hybrids run electrically. Fig. 6b and Fig. 6c analyse correlations between configurations and results. Fig. 6b plots houses on gas against line loading, with points coloured by time of day. The scatter shows weak correlation ($r = 0.11$): the same number of houses on gas can produce different loading levels depending on total demand at that time. Configuration versus cost is shown in Fig. 6c, which also exhibits time-dependent behaviour as opposed to a straightforward linear relationship.

The objective metrics demonstrate strong correlations: carbon and loading correlate at $r = 0.78$, in contrast to cost and loading, which correlate at $r = 0.88$. Because of this alignment, the goals frequently progress simultaneously. The optimal fuel allocation, however, is dependent on the interaction of demand, network state, prices, and carbon intensity at each time step, as confirmed by the weak correlation between configuration and loading ($r = 0.11$). A static rule such as “switch to gas when loading exceeds 80%” would not capture these dynamics.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results confirm that coordinating a small number of hybrid systems can resolve network violations that would otherwise block electrification. The 20 hybrids in this study represent just 20% of the neighbourhood, yet their coordinated flexibility eliminates the thermal limit exceedance caused by 30 heat pump households plus background load. Strategic deployment of hybrids on feeders approaching capacity could therefore support higher electrification rates than network reinforcement alone.

The priority-weighted reward function is central to this outcome. Allocating 60% of the weight to network stress ensures the controller never compromises infrastructure security for carbon or cost gains. The 15.7% emission reduction achieved here is smaller than unconstrained electric operation would deliver, but it comes without violations that would render such operation infeasible. In effect, the VHP trades some carbon performance for network viability.

Fig. 5 shows that the optimiser does not treat every house in the same way, according to the switching analysis. Houses H1 to H6 spend more time on gas, while H15 to H20 operate predominantly on electricity. Most likely, this pattern is caused by differences in grid position: when the network is

(a) Distribution of gas house count across all 30-min periods (mean 8.8).

(b) Network loading vs. gas house allocation, coloured by time of day.

(c) Heating cost vs. gas house allocation, coloured by time of day.

Fig. 6: Switching behaviour analysis.

overloaded, homes with heat pumps that are with the highest stress on the critical feeder are the first to switch to gas. By taking advantage of this diversity, the controller can meet the constraints with fewer switches than it would need for a uniform policy.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Virtual heat plants offer a practical mechanism for coordinating hybrid heating systems at the neighbourhood scale. Under the extreme cold conditions tested here, the MCTS-based controller eliminated electric network overload (reducing peak loading from 104.5% to 86.3%) while cutting carbon emissions by 15.7% relative to gas-only operation. Three findings merit emphasis. First, coordination of 20 hybrid households produces system-level benefits that no individual dwelling could achieve alone: the collective flexibility of the VHP resolves a constraint violation affecting the entire feeder. Second, network security and carbon reduction can conflict on high-demand days, making reward function design critical; the reward function prioritises infrastructure limits over economic and environmental objectives. Third, optimal fuel allocation varies continuously with demand, prices, and grid carbon intensity; the weak correlation between configuration and loading ($r = 0.11$) confirms that static switching rules would underperform.

Several extensions would strengthen these findings. The analysis examines a single extreme weather day; while this establishes value under critical conditions, a multi-scenario analysis across milder weather and shoulder seasons would strengthen annual extrapolation and establish how the VHP value varies with heating load. A systematic grid search for reward weight selection will be explored in future work to clarify whether alternative weightings better balance network security, cost, and carbon objectives. Characterising the Pareto frontier between network reliability and carbon objectives would clarify the trade-offs available to system operators. Finally, integration with real-time flexibility markets could allow VHPs to provide services beyond self-balancing, generating revenue that improves the economics of hybrid installations. As the UK accelerates heat electrification, coordination mechanisms of this kind will be essential for managing distribution networks through the transition.

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